

AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH TO MENSTRUAL HEALTH: A CLINICAL
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ABSTRACT

Menstrual symptoms refer to the set of symptoms associated with onset of cyclical menstrual blood flow. These include pain, breast tenderness, bloating, headache, nausea, diarrhea or constipation, anxiety, mood swings, irritability etc. Most common symptom among all is abdominal pain or dysmenorrhea. According to a study, conducted in 2016 in an urban city of south India, prevalence of dysmenorrhea was found to be 70.2%. Prevalence of menstrual pain is high among reproductive age group women. Dysmenorrhea in adolescent women badly affects their daily work and quality of life. In *Ayurveda* classics, it is mentioned, that one should observe specific lifestyle regime known as *rajaswala paricharya* during menstrual flow. Observance of this lifestyle regime leads to smooth symptomless menstrual flow. This lifestyle regime includes celibacy (*brahmcharya*), consumption of *Yavanna* (hordeum vulgare or barley) processed with cow milk as porridge, which should be consumed in moderation (not up to full satiety), should avoid day sleeping, sour, salty, hot food, and oil massage. In this review article, this lifestyle regime has been discussed and analyzed with special reference to menstrual symptoms.

KEYWORDS: menstruation, pain, lifestyle, diet, *rajaswala paricharya*.**INTRODUCTION**

Menstruation is defined as physiological cyclic monthly bleeding due to shedding of upper layer of uterine lining (endometrium) that occurs from female reproductive tract (vaginal tract) as a consequence of cyclic changes in hormonal activity (hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis).^[1,2,3,4] It results from cyclic process occurring in endometrial lining of uterus which includes repeated tissue injury and repair. Physiologically, menstruation involves balanced activity of proliferation, decidualization, inflammation, hypoxia, apoptosis, haemostasis, vasoconstriction and finally repair and regeneration.^[1,2,3,4]

The menstrual cycle occurring in females has been termed as *Rituchakra* in *Ayurveda*. Menstrual cycle in modern which is under control of Hypothalamus pituitary ovarian axis can be interpreted as *Rituchakra* under influence of *Prana vayu* (*prana vayu* acts as

central regulator simulating as hypothalamus)- *Udana vayu* (*shukragni* & *artavagni* get activated in presence of optimum *sneha*, which is ensured by *udana vayu srotopreenana karma*), *samana vayu* (ovary- *artavavaha srotovichari*) equilibrium where *artava nishkraman* process is controlled by *Apnana vayu* & normal *dhatu gati* and *shrotoshodhana* is attained by *vyana vayu*.^[5] This physiological process of menstruation cycle (*Rituchakra*) can be assessed clinically by symptoms of ovulation (*ritumati lakshan*) and menstrual blood characteristics (*shuddha artava lakshan*). As per *Ayurveda*, *Shuddha artava lakshan* (normal menstruation) are sign and symptoms of healthy menstrual blood flow which include its occurrence once in a month without pain and burning, excreted blood of menstruation should be thin watery (i.e. without clots), moderate in amount (neither scanty nor excessive), color resembling red lotus flower, red lac or blood of rabbit,

should not leave stain on clothes after washing with water.^[6]

Menstrual blood is known as *raja* or *artava* in Ayurveda.^[7] *Raja* is derived from essence part of *rasa dhatu* (plasma).^[8] Whole menstrual cycle (*ritukala*) can be divided into three phases *Rajahkala* (menstrual phase), *ritukala* (proliferative phase), *rituvyatita kaala* (secretary phase). *Rajahkala* or *rajahsrava* is of 3-5 days, manifested by menstrual blood flow, dominated by *vata dosha*. *Ritukala* is considered to be fertile period of cycle, manifested by establishment of *navina raja* (decidualization) and *ritumati lakshan* (sign and symptoms of ovulation), dominated by *kapha dosha*. *Rituvyatita kala* is dominated by *pitta dosha* and is manifested by constriction of *yonis* and does not accept *shukra* or permit entry of sperm.^[9,10] Hence, it can be interpreted that menstrual cycle is coordinated function of *tridosha*.

As per *ayurveda* classics, physiological healthy menstrual cycle can be assessed by *ritumati lakshan* and *shuddha artava lakshana*. Hence, it can be interpreted that menstrual flow should be symptom free and devoid of any pain or discomfort.

To keep menstrual flow healthy, symptom free some diet and lifestyle regimen is postulated in *Ayurveda* classics, known as *Rajaswala paricharya*. *Rajaswala* means menstruating women and *paricharya* means regimen.

In this review, components of *rajaswala paricharya* will be discussed with special reference to their potential in management of common menstrual problems.

METHODOLOGY

Databases PubMed, Google Scholar, *Shodhganga*, *Dhara*, *Ayush* portal were searched by using following key words in different combination "Menstruation", "Menstrual symptoms", "Ayurveda", "Diet", "lifestyle", "Celibacy" and Menstruation", "Day napping and Menstruation", "Barley", "Hordeum Vulgare", "Inflammation", "Dysmenorrhea". Classical Ayurveda Texts *Sushruta Samhita*, *Charak Samhita*, *Ashtang Hridaya*, *Ashtang Sangraha* and other relevant *ayurvedic* text books have been searched thoroughly for relevant topics.

COMMON MENSTRUAL SYMPTOMS AND THEIR PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

1. Pain- "Cramping pain which occurs just before or during menstruation in region of lower abdomen radiating to lower back and thighs, not associated with any other pelvic pathology is known as primary dysmenorrhea".^[11] If cramping pain occurs on or before menstruation due to some underlying pathology like endometriosis, pelvic inflammatory disease, uterine fibroid etc., then it is known as secondary dysmenorrhea.

According to a study conducted in 2016 in an urban city of south India the prevalence of dysmenorrhea was found

to be 70.2%.^[12] Dysmenorrhea in adolescent women badly affects their daily work and quality of life.^[13] There are several theories for pathophysiology of primary dysmenorrhea, but one of the most appropriate theory is increased synthesis of prostaglandins (types E2 and F2 α) which are produced through arachidonic acid cascade, mediated by cyclooxygenase (COX) pathway. Increased level of prostaglandin leads to vasoconstriction, ischemia resulting in dysrhythmic uterine contraction and pain.^[14] Progesterone hormone regulates formation of arachidonic acid, through the activity of lysosomal enzyme phospholipase A2. Rapid decline of progesterone just before onset of menstruation leads to release of lysosomal enzyme and thus formation of prostaglandin and pain onset.^[15]

2. Headache- Menstrual related headache occurs due to decline in estrogen during menstrual cycle. Estrogen is involved in serotonergic and glutaminergic system of CNS. Production of serotonin decreases with decrease in estrogen level in late secretary phase of cycle, which leads to increased substance P and calcitonin gene related peptide (CGRP) from trigeminal nerves. These substances cause vasodilatation of intracerebral vessels, and releases pro inflammatory mediator in pain sensitive meninges.^[16] This theory of pathogenesis of menstrual headache also get proved by fact that serotonin agonist are found to be effective in treating headache.^[17]

3. Mood swing, fatigue, depression, insomnia- Mood swings, fatigue and depression during menstruation are manifestation of estrogen serotonin regulation. A molecular biological study shows that decreased estrogen level during late secretary phase leads to release of nor-epinephrine from hypothalamus, which causes decline in serotonin, acetylcholine and dopamine leading to insomnia, fatigue, depression and mood swings.^[18]

4. Mastalgia- Cyclic mastalgia (breast pain) is due to hormonal variation during menstrual cycle. Periodic pain is due to increase in estrogen level during luteal phase that stimulate breast engorgement. Simultaneous increase in prolactin causes ductal swelling and secretion leading to tenderness in breast.^[19]

5. GIT symptoms- Common GI symptoms that affect during menstruation are nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, diarrhea, constipation, bloating. Studies suggest that GI symptoms are very common during menstruation and over 70% experience GI symptoms in conjunction with their menstrual cycle.^[20] Studies suggest that depression, pain and gut motility are associated probably through serotonin mediating pathway.^[21] Overproduction of prostaglandin may provide another pathophysiological link to understand. In gut, prostaglandin can cause smooth muscle contraction as well as reduced absorption and induced secretion of electrolytes in small bowel, all of which may enhance GI pain and diarrhea.^[22]

Rajaswala paricharya

In classics of Ayurveda, specific diet and life style regime has been mentioned for menstruating women known as *rajaswala paricharya*. According to *rajaswala paricharya*, from the day of onset of menstruation, lady should observe *brahmcharya* (celibacy), should avoid sleeping in day time, should avoid bathing, massaging (oil application), fast racing, laughing, talking too much, should not observe direct air or wind, should avoid excessive exercise and pungent (*tikshna*), hot (*ushna*) and salty diet. Menstruating lady should eat *havishya* (meal made of ghee, Sali rice and milk) or *yava* with cow milk (barley porridge with milk) in moderate amount or not up to full satiety in order to get her body *karshan* (emaciation) and *koshtha shodhan* (cleansing of GIT or uterus). She is advised to sleep on bed made of *darbha* or *kusha* grass (*darbhasanstar shayini*).^[23,24,25]

Most of the components of *rajaswala paricharya* are in accordance to maintain physiological *vata* state (*prakrita vata*). As *rajah srava kala* is dominated by *vata dosha*, So any factor which can increase *vata dosha* like talking too much, excessive exercise, fast racing etc. or any factor which pacifies or decrease *vata dosha* like hot pungent meal, massaging, oiling, bathing, day sleeping should be avoided.

Also menstruation is a state of cleansing, sloughing off where physiological process of autophagy is going on in uterus lining. So during this phase anything which is nurturing (*brimhana karma*) in nature should be avoided like oiling, bathing (head bath).

Basic component of Rajaswala Paricharya and their potential to cure menstrual Symptomology

- **Celibacy (*Brahmcharya*)** – Systemic review study (including 4 studies) shows that sexual activity during menstruation increases risk of endometriosis. Presence and growth of endometrial tissue anywhere outside uterus is known as endometriosis. Retrograde menstruation is considered as main etiologic factor for endometriosis. Sexual activity probably increases retrograde menstruation and thus chances of endometriosis. Endometriosis is leading cause of painful menstruation, menstrual irregularity and infertility. Thus celibacy during menstruation plays preventive role in maintaining good reproductive health in females.^[26,27,28,29,30]
- **Barley Porridge (*Yavanna*)**- *Yava* (hordeum vulgare) possess *ruksha guna* (dry), *kashaya*, *madhura rasa* (astringent, sweet in taste), *sheet veerya* (cold in potency) and *katu* (pungent) *vipaka*. By all these properties it has *kapha pitta shamaka* effect. It has cooling, *lekhan* (depleting, scraping), *anabhishtandi* (do not block channels) effect.^[31]

Use of *yavanna* in menstrual regime is for *karshan* and *shodhan* effect. *Yava* due to its *ruksha guna* and *lekhan* property induces apoptosis in endometrium leading to effective shedding of endometrium. Also *ruksha guna*,

koshtha shodhana (due to enhance quantity of faeces by *yava*) leads to *apana anuloman* and *prana* (hypothalamus) activation for next cycle.

Several studies observed vitamin B1, B6, Omega 3, magnesium is found to be effective in managing pain during menstruation. *Hordeum Vulgarae* also contains these micronutrients and thus can help in relieving menstrual pain.^[32]

Most of the symptoms of menstruation are due to overproduction of prostaglandin and decreased serotonin level. Laboratory experiments shows that barley inhibit both cyclooxygenase (COX) and lipoxygenase (LOX) pathway of arachidonic acid formation and thus has anti-inflammatory effect.^[33] Also barley contains phytochemicals including phenolic acid, flavanoids, lignans, tocopherols, phytoestrogen and folate, which exhibit strong antioxidant, antiproliferative, anti inflammatory properties.^[34]

Thus, barley by inhibiting prostaglandin synthesis have strong potential in relieving menstrual symptoms especially pain.

Also an animal study suggests that *Talibana* (traditional name for barley porridge) consumption causes rise in dopamine (DA), GABA and serotonin content. These studies give evidential support to hypothesis that barley consumption can relieve many menstrual symptoms like migraine, mood swings which are due to disturbed estrogen serotonin pathway.^[35]

Also a case report of an adolescent girl having PMS suggests consumption of green gram soup and barley porridge during first three days of menstruation for continuous six cycles improves lower abdominal backache, tenderness, constipation tiredness and mood swing.^[36]

Thus, all the literary and clinical evidence suggests barley porridge, one of the main component of *rajaswala paricharya* has strong potential in treating menstrual symptoms.

- **Avoidance of hot pungent salty diet**- As *rajahsrava kala* is dominated by *vata dosha*, so any diet which increase or vitiate or pacify *vata dosha* should be avoided. Hence, hot pungent salty diet which can pacify *vata dosha* should be avoided during *rajahsrava kala*. During menstruation, there is production of inflammatory markers like prostaglandins (types E2 and F2 α) which are produced through arachidonic acid cascade, mediated by cyclooxygenase (COX) pathway. Some observational studies suggest that anti-inflammatory or proinflammatory effect of phytochemicals are more related to their taste rather than their chemical constituent. And it suggested bitter taste has best association with anti-inflammatory activity

in contrast to other taste. Sour salty foods are associated with proinflammatory activity.^[37,38,39]

• **Avoidance of exercise-** As exercise or vigorous physical activity can vitiate *vata dosha*, so severe exercise is prohibited during menstruation as per *rajaswala paricharya*. A study was done to observe effect of 60 min cycling at 75% of their individual anaerobic threshold (AT) in circulating cytokines and leukocytes response during different phases of menstrual cycle which revealed that 60 min strenuous exercise may induce inflammation especially during menstrual phase.^[40] At the other hand some other studies suggests that regular exercise alleviate premenstrual symptoms.^[41] So effects of exercise during menstruation is inconclusive, yet it can be interpreted that regular exercise helps to alleviate menstrual symptoms but strenuous heavy exercise should be avoided during menstruation as it may increase inflammation as well as menstrual symptoms.

CONCLUSION

Physiologically menstruation is considered as inflammatory process induced by sudden decline of progesterone and estrogen hormone, marked by elevated levels of inflammatory markers like prostaglandin, chemokines, cytokines, metalloproteinases (MMPs).^[42] Immunohistochemical studies suggest activation of inflammasome NLR P3 in decidualized stromal cells and endometrial leukocytes resulting in inflammatory and proteolytic events resulting in tissue breakdown in endometrium. Chemokines IL1 beta and IL18 which are products of NLR P3 activation are elevated locally in endometrium as well as spread systemically leading to systemic inflammatory response. Thus it can be concluded that menstruation is a state of inflammation.^[43]

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